

Discover our latest updates

August 2023
Vol. 1

OPEN CALL 1

Launch on
October 2023

We will launch our 1st open call on October 2023

Selected participants will receive up to €200.000, guidance and support to develop their solution, access to experts and capacity building on extended reality (XR) technologies.

[Learn more](#)

Meet Alain Pagani, our project coordinator

Read our first scientific publications

Meet our CORTEX2 team

Keep up with our news!

Remote collaboration made easy with XR

At CORTEX2, we envision a world where remote collaboration is easy, efficient and accessible for all. We aim to facilitate it through next-generation eXtended Reality (XR) technology solutions across a wide range of industries and SMEs. To this end, we are developing an innovative XR platform, which will facilitate work and social activities involving physical interaction with the environment and remote objects.

OPEN CALL 1

**Launch on
October 2023**

 We will launch two open calls – the first one in October 2023 – to recruit and support European XR innovators in the co-development and replication of our platform. **In total, we will invest 4M€ in financial support for innovative solutions.**

Selected participants – from research-oriented institutions (technical universities, RTOs, spin-offs) to business-driven organisations (tech startups/SMEs, innovation units in large-scale industry) – will receive up to **€200.000**, guidance and support to develop their solutions, access to experts and capacity building on XR technologies.

Stay tuned to our channels for updates on when and how to apply!

[Learn more about our open calls](#)

Meet our project coordinator, Alain Pagani

“

After the world had to massively use video-conference tools due to COVID-19 restrictions, we developed the idea of a system that combines video-conferencing and eXtended Reality to generate cooperative experiences with better quality and higher impact.”

Alain Pagani, CORTEX² project coordinator and deputy director of DFKI's Augmented Vision Department

Funded by
the European Union

CORTEX²

Alain Pagani is our CORTEX2 project coordinator and the deputy director of the Department of Augmented Vision at the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (DFKI).

Learn about his motivations and background as an expert in computer vision, image understanding and artificial intelligence. Also, about his role in CORTEX2, his vision of the project and the positive impact it brings, as well as our main achievements and next steps.

[Read Alain Pagani's interview](#)

Discover our first scientific publications

[Extended Collaborative
Telepresence for Future Work
and Education](#)

Published at the Leading and Managing in the Digital Era (LMDE) International Conference.

Structure PLP-SLAM: Efficient Sparse Mapping and Localisation using Point, Line and Plane for Monocular, RGB-D and Stereo Cameras

Published at the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA).

X-RiSAWOZ: High-Quality End-to-End Multilingual Dialogue Datasets and Few-shot Agents

Published at Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL).

CORTEX²

Cooperative Real-Time Experiences with Extended reality

AUTHORS
Azucena Garcia Palacios | Alain Pagani | Raquel Carró / Andrea Torras

FUNCTIONS
Analysis of psychosocial factors to optimise CORTEX² | project coordinator | work package leaders Innovation strategy, dissemination, exploitation and PSP

EMAIL
contact@corTEX2.eu

ORGANISATIONS
Azucena Garcia Palacios - Universitat Jaume I | Alain Pagani - German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (DFKI) | Raquel Carró / Andrea Torras - AUTRALO

COUNTRIES
Spain | Germany | Estonia

FUNDING PROGRAMME
Horizon Europe

DURATION
01/09/2023 - 31/10/2025

WEBSITE
https://corTEX2.eu

SOCIAL MEDIA
https://twitter.com/corTEX2EU
www.linkedin.com/company/corTEX2EU
corTEX2.eu/press

Different advances in technology are taking place and are being explored to improve immersive learning, including the topic of CORTEX², extended reality (XR) collaborative experiences. CORTEX² aims to contribute to this goal with innovative tools (natural and flexible experience, semantic multi-channel fusion, integration of the Internet of things, IoT), with the end goal of democratising the access to remote collaboration offered by next generation XR experiences.

In line with the above, CORTEX² provides full support for augmented reality (AR) experiences as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices, through a novel Mediation Gateway platform.

- Resource-efficient teleconferencing tools through innovative transmission methods and the automatic summarization of shared long documents.
- Easy-to-use and powerful XR experiences with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings.
- Fusion of vision and audio for multichannel semantic interpretation and enhanced tools such as virtual conversational agents and automatic meeting summarization.

During its lifetime, CORTEX² will demonstrate the potential of fully interactive XR-based cooperation in several pilot areas, such as industrial production, business meetings and remote training.

During the development and testing of the tools, and parallel to technical validation, CORTEX² is taking into account important aspects like sustainability (reduced footprint) as well as the ethical, legal and social challenges of XR experiences. In fact, one basic pillar of CORTEX² is the analysis of the social impact associated with XR technology adoption, exploring psychosocial and ethical factors influencing social presence (stereographics like gender, culture, attitudes toward social experiences, agency etc.) and the possible negative effects involved in the use of XR, like technostress.

The mission of CORTEX² is to bridge the divide between widespread video-conferencing tools and state-of-the-art XR-based solutions, democratising the uptake of next-generation XR tele-cooperation among a large number of industrial segments and SMEs.

The COVID-19 pandemic pushed individuals and companies worldwide to work/study from home or change their working/teaching model, and disrupted education in over 150 countries, affecting 1.6 billion students. The share of employees who usually or sometimes work from home rose from 14.6% to 24.6% between 2019 and 2021 (Employment - census statistics, Eurostat, 2022). In Europe, the proportion of people working remotely rose from 5% to 40% as a result of the pandemic. Today, all the signs indicate that remote working is here to stay, with 72% of employees stating that their organization is planning some sort of teleworking in the future (2022 State of Remote Work, Buffer, 2022). But not all organizations are ready to adapt to this new reality, where team collaboration is vital.

According to the World Bank (Remote Learning During COVID-19: Lessons from Today, Principles for Tomorrow), for remote learning to be successful it needs to allow for meaningful two-way interaction between students and their teachers; such interaction can be enabled by using the most appropriate technology for the local context.

The use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) for remote working and learning has gradually taken hold in different areas of our lives. This can bring multiple benefits, such as greater access to learning and training, increased motivation towards different learning content, and greater diversity for entertainment, socializing, or the enhancement of creativity.

XR-PED
Project

REMOTE COLLABORATION
MADE EASY WITH XR

66
XR-PED
67

GREEN PAPER — EU PROJECTS

CORTEX2 in XRforPED's Green Paper

Our project appears in XRforPED's 'Green Paper' magazine. In an insightful article, we explain how CORTEX2 represents a pioneering effort to harness the power of XR technology for remote collaboration and learning, addressing technical, ethical, and social elements to ensure a sustainable and inclusive approach to future immersive experiences. [Read the article.](#)

Our CORTEX2 team

Our team brings together 10 organisations in 7 countries.

From academia and research organisations to technical ICT providers and SMEs, we bring expertise in XR, augmented and virtual reality, video-conferencing, AI, psychology and ethics.

10 partners · 7 countries

[Get to know us](#)

[Get in touch](#)

Your feedback is a gift to us!

Enjoy reading?
Forward this newsletter to a friend.

Keep up to date with our news!

Funded by
the European Union

This document has been created by the CORTEX2 project, which is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, which cannot be held responsible for them.

This email was sent to andrea@australo.org
You've received it because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

[View in browser](#) | [Unsubscribe](#)